

Gamification as an Intervention Tool in Psychosocial Support and Education of Primary School Students in Greece

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the Study: This study examines the method of Gamification, which involves the use of specialized games in non-gaming environments, aiming to modernize the education of primary school students and enhance their cognitive, emotional, and behavioral development. Furthermore, it explores Gamification as an alternative form of assessment as this method is attractive to students, and the educators' knowledge of this new method and its psychosocial implications.

Research Methodology: Qualitative research was employed for the analysis, utilizing semi-structured interviews. More specifically, in-depth interviews with primary school educators were conducted, followed by a content thematic analysis of their perspectives. **Findings:** The findings of this study indicate that educators believe that the Gamification method can significantly contribute to providing a better and more appealing educational process, but it requires them to receive better training so as to effectively implement it in practice.

Practical Implications: We hope that the findings of this study will be utilized by relevant authorities to fully integrate and implement the Gamification method in primary education structures. Additionally, this study highlights the need for educator training to effectively and successfully develop this new method.

Originality/Value: This research is significant and innovative for both Greek and international contexts, as it initiates the discussion on the full implementation of the Gamification method in the educational process of primary school students in Greece. Moreover, it explores, for the first time, the application of Gamification in the assessment and psychosocial enhancement of students in primary education..

Keywords: Gamification, Education, Diagnostic Assessment, Prevention, Intervention

Paper type : Research Paper

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, educators of all levels have been seeking new teaching methods. Their goal is to help students acquire learning skills, social skills, and life skills. It is perceived that the traditional way of teaching appears to be ineffective and no longer appealing to modern students surrounded by a multitude of digital devices. Educators face challenges related to students' motivation and engaging them actively in the classroom (Lee & Hammer, 2011).

The use of educational games, as learning tools and more, is a promising approach due to the many possibilities and impacts they have on children. Through play, we not only enhance a student's knowledge but also their social and life skills, such as problem-solving ability, communication, conflict avoidance, collaboration, etc. Gamification combines the characteristics of games, i.e. their mechanics, dynamics, and aesthetics, in order to increase the motivation for involvement as well as the development of critical thinking of students in the educational process (and not only in that process). Students acquire skills in a pleasant digital environment. (Sailer & Homner, 2020)

Games, in many respects, act as a driving force; they possess mechanisms that encourage children's involvement in educational processes as well as psychosocial support processes. However, a digital educational game is complex, time-consuming, and expensive (Kapp, 2012). Typically, educational games are created in a way so as to fulfill a set of learning and reinforcing goals. Success in classroom teaching requires specific infrastructure and appropriate knowledge on psycho-pedagogical integration, while the use of more specialized games requires more elements of thought and design, so that the incentives for unfettered participation of both students and educators are developed. These educators must be trained to apply these innovative techniques.

In this way, we are led to the formulation of the questions that govern the current research effort and which constitute the foundation for the emergence of the research purpose, as well as the individual research objectives of this study. More specifically, the research questions that were formed according to the bibliographic data and the research interests of the authors are related to the cognitive background and the training related to the topic of primary education teachers, their beliefs about the benefits of the gamification method and the students' response, the percentage of techniques used in the classroom, as well as the obstacles that arise during educational practice. Furthermore, the research questions of this study also include research on the utilization of the gamification method for the development of social skills and life skills in students, and the use of the method for diagnostic assessment and psychosocial intervention in students by the specialized educational staff of schools, namely psychologists and social workers. (Oliveira et al., 2022).

Thus, the purpose of this research effort is to study the exploitation of gamification in the field of education, and especially primary education, where it constitutes a brilliant field for early interventions and innovative practices, which will be particularly beneficial and essential for the course of students in all their subsequent stages of education and psycho-emotional completion.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 The Concept Of Gamification

Before someone delves deeply into gamification it is fundamental for them to understand what gamification is not.

Initially, gamification is not about turning everything into a game. It's the opposite. The principles of gamification state that whatever one wants to design one should not deviate from one's objective. In this case, the objective is learning. Gamification doesn't come to abolish or replace learning. On the contrary, it comes to make the learning process a better experience. A gamification system designer studies (and consequently learns from) games, and finds elements of games that enhance this experience and provide incentives to achieve the goal better. (Sailer & Homner, 2020)

Gamification is defined by (Deterding et al. 2011) as the use of game design elements in non-game contexts, rightfully being a new and rapidly developing field. The concept of gamification is different from that of an educational or entertainment game. Gamification applications, according to the above authors, simply use game elements to attract children so that educational and psycho-educational goals will be realized. The term gamification is relatively recent.

Another definition of gamification argues that it is the use of game logic and dynamics to solve problems and increase the audience's dependence on them (Zickerman & Cunningham, 2011).

Yet another definition states that gamification is the use of game elements and game-design techniques in an environment not meant for gaming (non-game context) (Werbach and Hunter, 2012). It's a concept that increasingly gains interest, making it a promising trend in many different sectors.

Additionally, gamification can be defined as the manifestation of various problem-solving activities and processes using game features. Even though typical game elements aren't entirely new, they have indeed become more common in contexts not related to games, typical cases being productivity tools, virtual task lists, business applications, digital marketing, and websites. Based on these elements, it can be understood that it involves the application of game design elements and game principles in non-game contexts (Lee & Hammer, 2011). In this context, it's believed that gamification works by using various techniques to exploit our natural desires, as well as to improve the way various activities or processes are implemented, both in education and in fields of social work and psychology (Antonopoulou, et al., 2022).

2.2 Game Mechanics

Game design is not done haphazardly. On the contrary, to design a successful game, one must use certain mechanisms thoughtfully and creatively, but also add one's own originality.

Every game is governed by certain mechanisms (game mechanics) which essentially help it evolve and move forward. They are the verbs, one might say, of game grammar. They describe the player's goal, the way in which the player can achieve that goal, and what will happen when the player gets there (Adams & Dormans, 2012).

Mechanisms facilitate and encourage the player to explore the game, create patterns of repetitive behavior and provide pleasure and entertainment (Simoës, Redondo, & Vilas, 2012).

Besides the term "mechanics", in the literature we also come across the term "techniques" (game techniques). This does not refer so much to the practices the designer will use, but to the approach to various challenges the player will face (Thom, Millen, & Di Micco, 2012).

Game mechanics are divided into three categories:

- Progression Mechanics,
- Feedback Mechanics, and
- Behavioral Mechanics.

They are used to reinforce feelings and behaviors, such as:

- ✓ engagement with the game,
- ✓ loyalty to the game,
- ✓ the time the player devotes,
- ✓ the influence of the game,
- ✓ the enjoyment the player derives,
- ✓ the use of user-generated content,
- ✓ the drive for inviting and the participation of many users (virality).

Such mechanisms are as follows: Challenges: Activities that challenge the player to solve them in order to progress further in the game.

- Chance: Often in a game, mechanisms based on luck are used, such as rolling a dice, drawing a face-down card, etc.
- Competition: Many games invite players to compete against each other in order to win something.
- Cooperation: In some games, collaborative activity is needed in order to overcome an obstacle.
- Player Feedback: A very important mechanism for games is player feedback. Especially in the early stages of the game, feedback can keep the player engaged so they don't get bored. Throughout the game, feedback often resolves questions the player might have.
- Resource Acquisition: Many games give the player the opportunity to acquire resources (materials), which they will need in a subsequent phase, either to trade them or to use them to build something in order to progress the game action to the next level.
- Rewards: Benefits that the player receives from the game as a gift or reward, depending on what they have achieved or how far they have progressed.
- Transactions: During many games, players are asked to buy or sell things (either virtual purchases or real ones). Sometimes, these transactions also concern exchanges of goods between players.
- Turn: In which order and under what conditions each player can play in the game.
- Win State: In every game, there are certain conditions that the player must meet in order to be designated as the winner (e.g., reaching a certain final level, collecting a certain number of points, etc.). (Thom, Millen, & Di Micco, 2012)

2.3 Game Elements And Rewards

Besides graphics and plot, every game contains certain elements, often shared among different games, aimed at defining the quality of experience the user derives. These elements are essentially the grammar of games. The most commonly encountered elements according to Werbach (2012) are:

- Points: This is the most widespread element. Found in a multitude of games, they often constitute the game's most crucial factor. Players strive to earn more and more points, as through these points:

- ✓they keep score,
- ✓level up,
- ✓make trades,
- ✓determine a winner,
- ✓compare the standing of two players within the game,
- ✓receive in-game rewards,
- ✓provide feedback to both the players and the designer,
- ✓track everyone's progress.

The point system in a game can include points from the following categories:

- ✓Experience Points: Points earned from a player's actions.
- ✓Redeemable Points: Points that can be exchanged within the game, enabling the player to gain something more significant they need.
- ✓Skill Points: Points a player can earn as a reward for achieving a particular activity.
- ✓Karma Points: Points that may be awarded if someone played three times consecutively within a month's span or points earned because they helped another player.
- ✓Reputation Points: Points given from one player to another that shape their reputation.

Rewards are a very important element of gamification. There are many different ways to give rewards, while at the same time there is a very large number of behaviors or achievements that can be rewarded. The purpose of rewards is the engagement and greater commitment of the players. Rewards are distinguished into three major categories (Kapp, 2012):

Tangible and Intangible: Tangible rewards are those rewards that are concrete, meaning they pertain to tangible (even virtual) objects, such as money, while intangible ones are all symbolic rewards (badges) or even verbal rewards (“good job!”).

Expected and Unexpected: Expected rewards are the rewards we know we will receive if we do something specific. Unexpected rewards are those that come as a surprise or arise from the element of chance and are more powerful precisely because we do not expect them.

Contingent Rewards: These rewards are given depending on the performance of an action. So, there are rewards that are given anyway in a game without any effort (task non-contingent), rewards given when an action is initiated (engagement-contingent), rewards given when an action is completed (completion-contingent), and rewards related to the quality and performance of the player (performance-contingent).

Thus, there are many possibilities, ways, and reasons to give rewards in a game. However,

what is important for the designer is to think about "when" to give them, so that they become effective incentives for further engagement of the player in the game. Usually, designers create a reward schedule to determine the time when rewards will be given. The most basic reward programs are (Glover, 2013):

- ✓Continuous Reward: In these programs, rewards are given very frequently over time.
- ✓Fixed Ratio Reward: In these programs, rewards are given at specific moments and at a specific pace, for example, the user is rewarded every time they increase their score by 100 points
- ✓Fixed Interval Reward: In these programs, rewards are given at specific times, regardless of whether the player has achieved something at that specific moment.
- ✓Variable Rewards: In these programs, rewards are given randomly and without the player expecting them (e.g., arising after rolling a dice).

2.4 The Benefits Of Gamification.

The educational and psychosocial benefits resulting from the application of gamification in the educational process become clear when analyzing the specific techniques that are applied in practice. Specifically, these techniques, borrowed from the "world of games," aim at and affect three areas that are essential for the multifaceted development of the student (Tzouvara, 2014):

Intellectual-Cognitive Area The application of traditional teaching methods appears problematic due to their inherent characteristics. Traditional teaching is rigid and structured within very narrow limits, thus providing limited flexibility for both students and educators. Additionally, and in alignment with the previous point, there is a demand for complete guidance of the students, which renders them passive and minimally active in a journey the direction or purpose of which they do not know. Recognizing the benefits arising from the educational process right from the start motivates students to participate. Finally, it's evident that the use of traditional methods does not favor the development and cultivation of the crucial metacognitive skills that are a lifelong asset.

The gamification method provides a solution to the above issues. When we deal with a new game, what we do is learn its rules and explore its potential through playing. In other words, using it leads us to knowledge of it.

We explore the world, the rules, and the limits of the game, and once we familiarize ourselves with them, we can continue. This is precisely where the key element of gamification lies. As in games, the student experiments and explores the newly provided knowledge through continuous challenges and short-term actions in a trial and error process until the skill is mastered and can move on to the next level (new skill). (Swacha, 2021) These challenges should be varied to cater to different learning styles and obviously are of escalating difficulty according to the development of the students' skills. Crucially, in order to motivate students and encourage enthusiastic student participation, there should be immediate ways of rewarding the achievement of a goal, instead of an indefinite long-term benefit. A reward could even be the presentation of an even more challenging problem to solve. (Blankman, 2022)

Emotional and Psychological Aspect: The notion of "failure" within a cognitive process is a common phenomenon. We learn through our mistakes. However, traditional teaching methods fail to handle the negative emotions that arise due to failure and error. The cost of failure is high, and feedback loops are extensive; therefore, the danger and the probability of failure intimidate, stress, and even inhibit students' desire to participate, leading, in some cases, to total withdrawal. In short, "failure" is demonized at the expense of learning. (Blankman, 2022)

Gamification offers a different perspective on the concept of "failure" or rather "not achieving a goal". It integrates it into the learning process as an inevitable yet concurrently useful occurrence. "Failure" in a game costs nothing, so students initially have a positive attitude towards the possibility of failure, knowing they can try again. Thus, they can turn failure into success through persistence. Here, feedback provided after every "failure" plays a crucial role, as does the fact that each challenge is designed to be manageable for the student-players. In conclusion, the goal finally achieved is the conversion of a negatively emotional experience into one that is positive and extremely useful.

Social Aspect: The typical learning process can be characterized as passive, individual/lonely, monotonous, and boring. The student feels they are part of a crowd, losing their personal characteristics that make them unique. They feel they're moving passively on a solitary path, and their minor or major achievements aren't recognized.

The "world of games" again shows us the way. Through the vast number and variety of challenges present in a game, everyone can showcase their skills and unique characteristics, building an identity. However, even more important is the fact that they can try on new roles and identities, something that rarely happens under real conditions, thus exploring other facets of themselves and enriching their personality. Group missions might be included in a game's framework. Participation in these enhances cooperation among the student-players, responsibility, and a sense of belonging. Lastly, the social recognition (within the micro-society of the class) offered by the acknowledgment of academic achievements is very important. This fact alone could motivate and mobilize students to intensify their efforts to achieve similar recognition and "social validation". (Willig, et al., 2021)

2.5 The Risks Of Gamification.

Gamification employs the logic of games. The most important elements of games are fun, pleasure, and joy. If these are missing from a game, no matter how well-designed it is, it will become boring, and players will seek something else. A gamified activity should operate in the same manner, focusing primarily on the aspect of entertainment (Papázoglou Papazoglákis, 2013).

Focusing specifically on the gamification of the educational process, we can identify certain risks:

Students, in order to engage in any process, need to see it as a challenge that leads to short, achievable, and clear objectives. However, students are also expected to participate in various contests and compete against one another. If educators aren't careful, competition can become antagonism. If intense rivalry emerges and one participant is significantly weaker than the rest, the situation could lead to negative outcomes. The student might feel marginalized and

incapable of meeting the challenges set before them and might even become a victim of bullying by their peers. (Blankman, 2022)

Furthermore, if there are leaderboards and a student consistently ranks at the bottom, or has not won any badges, there is a high chance they'll become disheartened. This could lead them to even resent the specific activity and the subject of learning more broadly.

Additionally, the method of gamification increases minors' time in front of a screen, to which they are already exposed for several hours through their other activities. This creates escalating conditions of screen addiction, gaming, and internet usage, with all the negative consequences this can entail.

Therefore, while the entire process of gamifying a lesson is interesting and is initially considered positive – since it provides incentives, motivates, involves the students, and makes the learning method effortless, fun, and effective – educators should not forget the risks hidden in this process. They should strive at every step to minimize these risks, aiming mainly at promoting healthy competition, teamwork, the socialization of students, and, finally, their cognitive progress. (Antonopoulou, et al., 2022)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present research aims to investigate the opinions and perceptions of primary education teachers regarding the significance and usefulness of gamification in contemporary schools. To achieve the purpose and specific objectives of this study, a qualitative research approach was chosen. Although the primary technique of qualitative research is intrinsically linked to the communication skills of the researcher, whose involvement may alter the outcomes of the topic under investigation, it is also known for its limitations in terms of generalizability and comparison (Iosifidis, 2017). By definition, the nature of qualitative research is fundamentally associated with a deep exploration of a matter, in detail, allowing the researcher to "see" and understand the world through the eyes of the social subjects of the study (Iosifidis, 2017). Thus, the researcher is both burdened and privileged to identify research subjects that can assist him/her in better approaching the topic under investigation (Creswell, 2012). It is worth noting that the qualitative research methodology should be chosen when there is insufficient data on the subject being explored, as well as when research questions seek to answer the "how" and "why" rather than the "how much" (Kyriazi, 2011) Finally, qualitative research aims for a broader, flexible, and open design (Kyriazi, 2011) to freely express the views, experiences, and stories of the participants, in contrast to the quantitative method that imposes a stricter and more structured design, organization, and execution of the research with less room for modification in its progress.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND RESEARCH TOOL

Based on the literature review that preceded the research design and in order to achieve the research purpose and the specific goals of the present study, the following research questions were formulated:

- What is the cognitive background and the level of training of primary education teachers (P.E.) in Greece regarding gamification?
- Do primary education teachers (P.E.) utilize gamification techniques to support the

educational and psychosocial process?

- What are the views of primary education teachers (P.E.) regarding the benefits and the response of students to the use of gamification techniques in the classroom and in counseling support services?
- What difficulties and obstacles do primary education teachers (P.E.) face concerning the application of gamification techniques?

To answer the above research questions, the most appropriate method (research tool) selected was the interview with the use of a structured questionnaire. It consists of a set of predefined questions posed during a face-to-face communication, with the interview guide including multiple questions which set the ground to explore the research questions as in-depth as possible (Iosifidis, 2017). The interview procedures were carried out based on a specially designed interview protocol, which was formed after studying the relevant literature, aiming to cover the research objectives of our study as comprehensively as possible. For the recording and safe storage of the interview material, a special mobile phone application was used.

5. RESEARCH SAMPLE AND SAMPLING METHOD

As already mentioned, in order to find answers to our research questions, we used structured interviews. The population used consisted of 8 primary school teachers in the Kavala Prefecture of Greece. The sampling that followed in order to locate these educators is a very significant process in the context of research design. This is because the chosen sample determines the quality of data to be collected and thus the conclusions that are to be drawn from any given study (Isari and Pourkos, 2015).

In the context of conducting qualitative research, like this one, the sample does not need to be representative of the general population, nor does the sampling process need to be objective, as is the case in quantitative research. Moreover, the aim of a qualitative research is not the general and objective characteristics (Mantzoukas, 2007). In this qualitative study, the participants come from a convenience sample, consisting of eight (8) primary education teachers from the Kavala Prefecture who work in primary schools in Kavala. They have significant experience and relatively good knowledge, in relation to others, on the subject under consideration. This selection was deliberately based on the availability of educators who expressed willingness to participate in this study, which is why we refer to it as a convenience sample. Nonetheless, it consists of educators with significant experience in the field.

Before the official conduct of the research and after compiling the interview guide, two (2) pilot interviews were carried out with two other educators working in Primary Education in Kavala. Each interview lasted approximately 45-50 minutes, and our research was conducted in January and February of 2023.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through the appropriate processing of data collected from the interviews of eight (8) educators, significant data was identified that answered the four basic research questions of this study. Specifically, as already noted, these questions initially pertained to the current and

potential knowledge background of educators concerning gamification in education, as well as whether educators utilize gamification techniques to support the educational process. Furthermore, they referred to the educators' views on the benefits and students' response to the use of gamification techniques in the classroom, as well as the difficulties and obstacles educators face in implementing gamification techniques in the classroom.

Regarding the first question, three main themes were identified based on the educators' responses, which relate to the correlation of familiarity with the educational process, the applications or digital platforms, and the training of educators. For most educators (6 out of 8), the term "gamification" is almost unknown, even though many of them use games and computers in the educational process.

The contribution of the internet to the utilization of gamification is also considered significant, even though educators do not often participate in seminars or training programs to exploit the potential of the internet. This highlights the need for their training in modern tools and applications.

Subsequently, attempting to answer the second research question, it was deemed necessary to identify two themes related to the frequency of familiarization with the concept of gamification and its utilization as an educational tool. In this context, research participants referred to their limited familiarization with it but also to the positive aspects of its implementation in the educational process, emphasizing the enhancement of the experiential nature of gamification. Equally important is the reference to the way they utilize it in the curriculum and how it is used by other educators.

Two additional axes were identified within the context of the third question, attempting to analyze the role of gamification techniques and evaluate their future use. Based on their answers, their importance was highlighted and simultaneously the high degree of student responsiveness was emphasized. Moreover, the focus was on the positive reaction of the students, as well as the educators' prediction of their more extensive use in the future. Similarly, within the context of the fourth question, two axes were identified, concerning the challenges of educators and how successful gamification implementation can be achieved in the future. Specifically, the most significant problems educators face in the classroom are purely practical and relate to limited equipment, while, regarding their other problems, emphasis was placed on inadequate training and their limited time due to curriculum issues. They also focused their interest on children with learning difficulties, for which the use of gamification is deemed important. Finally, they highlighted their need and desire for training, so as to facilitate and promote the effort of effective gamification use in primary education.

In an attempt to comment on the above findings, there is an apparent status quo, along with a tendency for change. The new generation of educators acknowledges that new technology is an integral part of students' everyday life. Education, trying to provide learning incentives, continuously seeks new teaching models. Therefore, capitalizing on this trend embodied by the term "gamification," educators foresee its necessary integration into daily educational practice in the classroom.

However, to steer things in this direction, the following steps (Fyssas & Avdelidou, 2016) are essential:

a) Systematic selection of material by the Pedagogical Institute.

- b) Training of educators and the application of selected digital games in the educational process. However, there lies the challenge, as many educators lack specific expertise or training in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) and, more specifically, digital teaching platforms. ICT should be used in class as supervisory tools, cognitive tools, tools for searching - finding information, and as tools of the daily work done at school. On the other hand, gamification is not integrated into the school's curriculum or the cross-thematic unified study program of the Pedagogical Institute.
- c) The replacement of outdated and unsuitable technological equipment.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Given the results of this study, it becomes evident that the application of gamification in the educational process, as well as in the psychosocial support of students, has not yet been implemented to a significant extent. Both the educators who participated in our research and the specialized educational staff (social workers and psychologists) do not yet have a clear methodological framework for the implementation and evaluation of gamification in the educational and psycho-pedagogical process. What has been done so far involves isolated efforts by educators and specialists, which either arise from specific training they have received or from personal motivations for development and improvement of the educational process.

In addition, according to the educational staff who participated in this study, the introduction of gamification now more consciously represents a method potentially suitable for more experimentation, or at least for efforts to overcome practical obstacles and integrate it into the learning routine. Undoubtedly, there emerges a necessity for further exploration of the introduction of the gamification method in the educational process, either by extending the current study or by conducting related research associated with the concept of gamification.

Delving into the research results, participants seemed not to have a clear understanding of the terminology surrounding gamification, with some guessing its content and others unable to interpret the term at all. It was indeed striking that the majority of educators have used digital interventions in their lessons or are aware of digital platforms and software designed to support the educational process, but are unaware of the relevant terminology. In an attempt to connect the data with the guidelines of the theoretical part, it's worth noting that in no case do educators seem to have knowledge of, or have taken into account the basic design principles that digital educational games should follow to effectively meet educational and psycho-pedagogical goals. Apparently, educators utilize material suggested by some official source, like the Ministry of Education, or that has already been used by their colleagues in other contexts.

Regarding the frequency of using such material, statistics are low, and the same goes for the variety in terms of alternating the use of gamified learning environments. Nevertheless, most participants were aware of other educators, mainly of the same specialization, who employed gamification techniques, at least as they understood the concept and its content up to that point.

Regarding the training of educators in gamification, none of the participants had relevant specialization, while most of them mentioned some course or unit as part of undergraduate or

postgraduate studies that happened to be generally related to technologies in education. However, all participants recognized the method as significant and in direct alignment with technological and social relevance. They stressed the necessity of providing further training to the community of educators and declared their own willingness to be substantially enriched with knowledge and material.

Concerning the benefits of the gamification method, and in agreement with the findings of Iosup & Epema (2014) and Robertson & Miller (2009), all educators unanimously responded that technological tools activate students' interest and attention in the classroom, provide learning incentives, cater to the different intelligences of children due to the experiential multi-sensory nature of the games, and can encourage collaboration and participation of children with learning difficulties. However, referring to the drawbacks, educators mentioned the practical issues related to small classrooms, that is lack of infrastructure and technological equipment, and the number of students per class that deprive students of focus and rich learning stimulation. It's worth noting that, in certain international studies we examined, the issue of insufficient equipment does not arise, and this specific problem seems to be primarily located in Greece, compared to other European and American countries. Secondly, although a study by Nah et al. (2013) raised concerns about the effectiveness of the goals and the level of difficulty, no similar concerns emerged in this specific research.

Furthermore, the Curricula and Study Programs do make references to technological means, but without specific guidelines. Some educators even state that the demands for covering the syllabus are quite extensive, and as a result the time left for more alternative teaching methods and tools significantly diminishes. Nevertheless, in light of the pandemic, the Institute of Educational Policy has suggested some platforms, created some proposed teaching scenarios, and organized a seminar-based training, but at a much later time than when the need for them was pressing.

In subsequent questions posed and related to the obstacles and difficulties, the interviewees mainly mentioned problems that were mentioned above. Regarding their students, there was some hesitation in terms of collaboration between them, the parents and their receptiveness to new educational means, and the tendency of children, sometimes, to get so excited that they misinterpret the lesson time as playtime. As for the last reference, there is agreement with the research of Rojas et al. (2013), which shows the partial tendency of some students to underestimate the importance and interest of lessons that do not utilize technological means, highlighting the position of technology in the lives of younger generations.

Compared to the issue of solving problems that may arise when using gamification tools in the classroom, participants did not focus so much on the problems themselves, but rather on the importance of the atmosphere or the role of the educator, on the one hand, in terms of his/her preparation, and on the other hand, in relation to his/her auxiliary and explanatory role in the classroom. Additionally, they strongly emphasized the need for their support from the Ministry, with the introduction of bills regarding classroom operations and their equipment, and also the training of technologically literate educators.

The above findings underscore in every way how far educational theory is from educational practice and how slowly innovations are integrated into educational practice, as well as the demands of scientific, technological, and social reality. In any case, the attitude of educators

and students is positive, with the former being aware of the difficulties and obstacles and continuing to express their willingness to be trained and integrate new techniques into their educational planning, while the latter (students) are fully familiar and flexible in handling technological means, as they grow at a parallel pace with them, and their interest is skyrocketing.

Although it would be wrong to generalize the findings of this research, given the limited sample of educators on which they were based, they still seem to realistically correspond to the data of the Greek public school with its perennial problems.

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